

Review of Mining and Sanitation Waste Water Management and Their Contribution to Water Contamination in Zambia

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Abstract:

This research digs into the convoluted topography of water contamination in Zambia's Copperbelt Province, with an emphasis on the important contributions of mining and sewage effluent. This report provides major conclusions about the origins, types, and effects of contaminants in the region's water bodies based on a thorough review of current research and empirical evidence. Mining activities emerge as a major source of water pollution, with effluent contaminated with heavy metals, sulphates, and other compounds that pose serious hazards to aquatic ecosystems and public health.

Despite efforts to improve wastewater treatment, shortcomings persist, resulting in the leakage of toxic effluent into neighboring waterways. Similarly, sewage wastewater contributes to contamination by including faecal coliforms, nutrients, oils, and heavy metals. The effects of water contamination are far-reaching, as indicated by increasing pollutant concentrations in stream sediments and downstream bodies. Aquatic life suffers from habitat destruction, diminished biodiversity, and negative health effects, while communities relying on these water supplies face increased health risks. Given these issues, the paper analyses potential solutions and recommendations for effective wastewater management, with a focus on interdisciplinary collaboration, technical innovation, and regulatory enforcement. Initiatives fostering recycling, resource recovery, and the implementation of advanced treatment technology hold promise for minimizing water pollution and maintaining sustainable water management practices in the Copperbelt Province.

Keywords: *mining, sanitation, effluent, pollution, human health.*

Introduction

Zambia's economy is primarily reliant on water resources for social development; nevertheless, successful management necessitates an awareness of local water availability. Drought and resource deterioration impede water governance. The 2010 revised National Water

Policy incorporates contemporary water management principles, tackles poverty reduction, and includes measures such as the National Decentralization Policy. The mining industry benefits national and local economies, yet it presents issues if not managed effectively (Hamed et al., 2024; Takam Tiamgne et al., 2022; Uhrendhal et al., 2011; Zabre et al., 2021).

Mining activities have a detrimental environmental impact, including water contamination. Wastewater treatment is becoming increasingly important as public awareness of environmental conservation and care grows (Smarzewska & Morawska, 2021). The issue of water shortage is critical because it involves wastewater, which comprises used liquids, solutions, colloids, suspensions, waste solids, industrial waste, food, and faeces from households that are discharged into natural

catchments or waterways (Smarzewska & Morawska, 2021; Topare et al., 2011).

Wastewater is collected from numerous sources usually via sewers and transferred to treatment plants, where it is classified based on source and pollutant strength, which varies depending on the generating source (Ahmed et al., 2017). Table 1 provides a brief summary of the six major sources of waste water grouped by importance.

Table 1. Waste Water Classifications Based on Their Sources

Domestic waste water	Industrial waste water	Agricultural waste water	Storm water runoff	Hospital/pharmaceutical waste water	Landfills leachate
Households, commercial	Mining	agricultural waste water	Rain water, inflow/ infiltration	Wastes contaminated with health care waste	Leachate generated from land fills
	Petroleum refining				

General Sources of Water Pollution

Industrial wastewater, agricultural wastewater, rainfall runoff, hospital pharmaceutical wastewater, and landfill leachate are all contributors to water contamination. Industrial effluent, contains treatment-resistant compounds and heavy metals. Agricultural wastewater, produced during irrigation and post-harvesting activities, contains suspended particles and pollutants. Storm water runoff collects various pollutants, while hospital-pharmaceutical wastewater introduces emerging contaminants into the environment. Landfill leachate contains harmful compounds and contaminants, highlighting the importance of proper management measures (Abdel-Shafy et al., 2024; Cisneros, 2011; Hamlyn-Harris et al., 2019; Raut et al., 2023; Samal et al., 2022).

Mine Waste Water

Mining wastewater discharged into the environment, contains hazardous pollutants like flotation agents and metal ions, which poses a significant environmental threat by polluting water supplies and harming ecosystems, thereby raising public concern (Matebese et al., 2024). Management on the Copperbelt Province of

Zambia typically involves treating the wastewater on tailings dams until it is fit for reuse or discharge into the environment.

Sanitation Waste Water

The most prevalent kind of wastewater that fits into the low-strength waste stream category is municipal wastewater. Low organic strength and high particle organic matter content are its defining characteristics (Sikosana et al., 2019). Sewage, a contaminated component of water, can present health problems because it is found in a variety of locations, including homes and business spaces. Installing sewage tanks and maintaining personal hygiene, such as washing hands with soap, are examples of sanitary measures to prevent this. Municipal wastes, which are normally disposed of via pipes or sewage lines, sometimes contains untreated sanitation waste water containing water, nutrients, sediments, pathogens, helminthes, oils, greases, runoff, heavy metals, and toxic compounds. If not treated before disposal, this water can have negative environmental consequences, including the emission of dangerous chemicals such as PCBs, PAHs, dioxins, furans, pesticides, and chlorinated organic compounds.

Examples of Water Pollution from Mining and Sanitation on the Copperbelt Province of Zambia

Mining, industrial discharges, urban growth, and agricultural runoff all contribute significantly to water pollution in Zambia's Copperbelt Province. The Czech Research Group, in partnership with the University of Zambia and the Geological Survey of Zambia, undertook a study from 2002 to 2018 to investigate pollution sources, soil and agricultural contamination, and river water and sediment contamination levels. The study discovered that copper and cobalt mining are common, but other trace elements

such as lead, arsenic, cadmium, and mercury have also accumulated in soils and stream sediments. Soil and crop contamination from mining dust and smelter emissions, as well as watercourse pollution caused by tailing dam leaks and pipeline breakdowns, are major concerns. The study discovered that contamination of the Kafue River water is fairly limited due to its strong self-purification capacity, although particular tributaries near mining centres had significant quantities of dissolved copper and cobalt, which exceeded Zambian effluent regulations (Křibek et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Africa Map Showing Location of Zambia and the Copperbelt Province

D. Limpitlaw's investigations in Zambia's Copperbelt region revealed elevated amounts of sulphate, copper, and zinc in surface water downstream of mining activity. These contaminants endanger aquatic life in certain areas but do not destroy them entirely. Runoff from tailing dams and waste rock dumps is high in heavy metals and acidity, causing environmental problems. Wastewater from mining production is often disposed of in tailings dams, contaminating surface water with

suspended particles and heavy metals. During the rainy season, heavy rainfall can cause tailings impoundments to overflow, potentially harming water bodies, river sediments, and aquatic life. Although no tailings impoundment overflows have been recorded in the Kitwe area, mine effluent from both open-pit and underground operations is discharged into the Kafue River, carrying a significant load of suspended and dissolved solids, indicating that receiving waters are not adequately protected from

contamination. High copper concentrations in effluents have resulted in the eradication of animal life and large reductions in algae and fungal populations in some locations (Limpitlaw, 1998).

Ondra Sracek et al. investigated the pollution of the Kafue River network in the Copperbelt. The study discovered that stream sediments in the Kafue River and its downstream tributaries were substantially higher in copper above the limits for freshwater sediments. Sequential investigations found that the extractable fractions included higher quantities of copper, cobalt, and manganese than the residual fraction. The pH values in the contaminated zones were found to be alkaline, and sulphate concentrations gradually increased downstream. Despite large copper and cobalt inputs from various pollution sources, most metals were bonded to suspended particles and deposited in the Kafue River. Other pollution sources around Kitwe, such as the Uchi mine tailings and the Nkana smelter, also contributed to metal release, but the metals were mostly in suspension and

attenuated well. The mineralogical composition of stream sediments downstream of Chingola revealed the existence of native copper, Cu-sulfides, Cu carbonates, and Cu linked to Fe(III) oxides and hydroxides (Sracek et al., 2012).

Waste Water Treatment Processes

Wastewater treatment aims at removing dangerous compounds from water before it is returned to the environment. It entails restoring water resources and safeguarding the environment from toxins' detrimental impacts. Inadequate or inappropriate treatment can cause water pollution, harming aquatic life and biodiversity (Matebese et al., 2024). Wastewater treatment consists of four major stages: screening, coagulation, sedimentation, and disinfection. The wastewater is either released into the environment or reused. The technology employed is determined by the source and amounts of recognized contaminants. Figure 2 depicts conventional waste water treatment stages.

Figure 2. Conventional Waste Water Treatment Process

The principle and stages behind treatment for both mining and sanitation waste water are similar with minimal differences due to

differences in predominant pollutant concentrations.

Mining Waste Water Management on the Copperbelt Province of Zambia

The Copperbelt Province of Zambia, a large metallogenic zone, is a major mining hub, with the Kafue River and its tributaries traversing the area. Wastewater discharge from mining waste and metallurgical slag deposits, as well as seepage from active tailings ponds contributes significantly to the river's and stream contamination (Sracek et al., 2012). Mining operations produce wastewater from mine water, process wastewater, residential wastewater, and surface runoff. This wastewater contains physical contaminants such as suspended solids, turbidity, color, temperature, taste, and odor, organic chemicals such as coal, oils, grease, soaps, detergents, rubber, dyes, and phenolic compounds, inorganic chemicals such as heavy metals, acids, alkalis, cyanide, dissolved salts, and anions, biological contaminants such as bacteria, viruses, and small organisms, and radiological contaminants such as uranium and tritium from mine tailings. These chemicals raise environmental concerns (Matebese et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2021).

Zambia's copper mining sector is mostly concentrated in the Copperbelt Province, where two significant firms serve as economic indicators. Mining accounts for about 90% of the country's GDP, with the Copperbelt Province as the largest source. Medium and small-scale mining firms also contribute to Zambia's copper production. However, waste water treatment systems utilised in these mines are expensive since tailings are carried great distances and required extensive land areas to settle. (Aurélien et al., 2022).

The majority of mines in Zambia's Copperbelt Province generate and release waste water, which has an impact on surface and groundwater resources. Tailing storage facilities (TSFs) are intended to store these byproducts, composed of crushed rock and processing fluids. These tailings generated during the extraction of rich minerals, metals, and mineral fuels, can contain hazardous pollutants and are much more in quantity than the released resource (Kossoff et al., 2014). Tailings, which are released as a slurry

in TSFs, are made up of waste particles, chemicals, and water, as well as other additives used in mining operations. As a result, appropriate waste water treatment is critical for protecting human health and the environment, as tailings contain surfactants, leaching agents, reagents, solvent extractants, and antioxidants (Mohapatra & Kirpalani, 2016). Tailings storage facilities are equipped with sedimentation basins to settle suspended particles prior to water release. pH adjustments and coagulants are used to improve waste water treatment operations. Metal precipitation with limestone and lime is based on metals' insolubility in alkaline conditions. Metals such as Cu, Mn, Fe, and Zn precipitate best at pH levels ranging from 6 to 9. Hydroxides and other metals require a pH over 10-12. Sulphates can be eliminated by precipitating gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), which has a solubility as low as 1200 mg/L and regulates SO_4 concentration levels (Bernard C. Aubé, 2003; Geldenhuys et al., 2003; Ngulube, 2016). This waste water treatment approach is expensive as it includes installing pipes and pumps to convey slurry from the process plant to the tailings dump, as well as maintaining dumps to avoid failure and environmental problems (Herza & Phillips, 2017).

Limitations of the Mining Waste Water Treatment Processes

Tailings Storage Facilities (TSFs) are popular mining waste water treatment facilities, however they have limits. They are built for containment rather than treatment, and they lack complete methods for dealing with toxins. Their ability to handle heavy metals, chemical substances, and microorganisms is restricted (Lottermoser, 2010a, 2010b).

Sanitation (Sewage) Waste Water Treatment

The fast rise of industry and population has resulted in increased wastewater production from mining plants and municipalities, posing a risk to human health and industrial processes. Pollutant removal requires a quick, simple, ecologically friendly, and effective process (Gangaraju et al., 2021). In Zambia, local governments are in charge of eliminating contaminants from sewage waste and providing

water and sanitation services to communities. According to the 2022 water supply and sanitation sector report, they have established companies in the copperbelt province, including Nkana Water Supply and Sanitation Company Limited (NWSSL), Kafubu Water Supply and Sanitation Company Limited (KWSSL), and Mulonga Water Supply and Sanitation Company Limited (MWSSL), which serve three towns each (www.nwasco.org.zm) ("National Water Supply And Sanitation Council (NWASCO) Sector Report 2023 ", 2023). The National Water Supply and Sanitation Council (NWASCO) actively supervises and regulates water utility firms' production and service delivery operations. Firms have developed sewage treatment facilities in all areas they serve to ensure that waste water is treated before it is discharged into the environment ("National Water Supply And Sanitation Council (NWASCO) Sector Report 2023 ", 2023). Major contaminants found in sewage waste water include COD, NH₃-N, TN, TP, faecal coliforms, sulphates, fluorides, and heavy metals. Untreated sewage can leak from manholes, causing health hazards. Sewer systems handle rainwater and urban sewage, but sewer overflow is a serious threat to the environment and human health due to wastewater discharge (Owolabi et al., 2022).

Conventional sewage treatment plants

Sewage treatment plants employ a settling tank or clarifier to remove settle able materials from wastewater. The most popular design in Zambia's Copperbelt province is circular. There are two kinds of clarifiers namely main and secondary. Primary tanks remove suspended items from influent wastewater, and secondary clarifiers recover biomass from processed effluent. Secondary clarifiers are often installed downstream of the biological treatment plant to ensure that wastewater is treated efficiently (Voutchkov, 2005). Trickling filters (TFs) are wastewater treatment devices used in the secondary stage. They are made of solid, inert materials such as gravel, rock, coke, porcelain, or plastic. Pollutants permeate through TF once wastewater is sprayed on it. External mechanical or gravitational forces are used to maintain a continuous flow of wastewater. As the biofilm

grows, bacteria absorb dissolved organic molecules, allowing it to proliferate. Metals can be adsorbed, and other interactions can be formed to eliminate pollutants (Dubey & Kashyap, 2022). Private individuals and organisations utilise sewage treatment technologies such as septic tanks, soakaways, and pit latrines in peri-urban regions, which can cause public health problems due to toxins seeping into groundwater sources (Gwenzi et al., 2023).

Conventional sewage treatment systems use activated sludge procedures and modifications to decompose nutrients, suspended particles, and organic materials. The main phases for removing sewage levels are preliminary, primary, second, third, and fourth stage or enhanced wastewater treatment. Compressors deliver oxygen to heterotrophic, nitrifying, and phosphate-accumulating bacteria in sewage treatment facilities. Conventional sewage treatment is difficult to execute since it is energy-intensive and demands considerable financial inputs (Yang et al., 2022).

Stabilization ponds

Waste stabilization ponds are a popular wastewater treatment solution due to their low maintenance costs, low energy requirements, and ease of operation. Microbes aid in the breakdown of organic detritus in these ponds and play an important role in physical, chemical, and biological processes (Rigotto et al., 2023). There are four types of pond systems namely: facultative ponds, anaerobic ponds, facultative aerated lagoons, and complicated mix aerated pond lagoons. Bacteria in soluble and fine particle BOD stabilize it aerobically, whereas suspension BOD settles and is transformed anaerobically by bacteria at the bottom. Algae employ photosynthesis to provide oxygen to aerobic microorganisms (Mahapatra et al., 2022; Muñoz & Guieysse, 2006; Sperling.). The Anaerobic pond-Facultative pond system transforms 50-70% of BOD in the deeper, smaller anaerobic pond, while the remainder is eliminated in the facultative pond, which is less in size than one decorative pond (Sperling.). A facultative aerated lagoon removes BOD in the

same way as facultative ponds do, but oxygen is given by mechanical aerators. Inadequate aeration allows biomass and sewage particles to settle and undergo anaerobic degradation near the bottom (Sperling.). A complete-mix aerated lagoon sedimentation pond expends significant energy to equally distribute materials, primarily biomass, in the liquid medium, resulting in total mixing. This enhances biomass concentration, improves BOD removal efficiency, and reduces pond volume as compared to facultative aerated lagoons. However, before effluent is released, it must be cleansed of settleable items that can be removed in the sedimentation pond. The sedimentation pond's sludge must be cleansed every few years (Sperling.). Maturation ponds are used to eradicate dangerous organisms such as coliforms by controlling environmental conditions such as UV exposure, high pH and DO, low temperature, nutrient deficiency, and predation by other species. These ponds constitute the post-treatment phase in the BOD removal process, and they are often designed as sequences or single baffle ponds with great efficiency (Sperling.).

Conventional municipal wastewater treatment facilities are simple and reliable, particularly in small land areas, but they require frequent maintenance and have limitations such as space requirements, odour emissions, low efficiency, and high energy use. Stabilization ponds provide several advantages, including ease of construction, low cost, minimum maintenance, adaptation to hydraulic stresses, and treatment of a wide range of wastewater kinds. However, they require a large amount of acreage, suffer with high BOD and TSS levels due to algae, have long retention times, produce biogas, and have insufficient nutrient removal capabilities (Sikosanaa et al., 2019; "Waste water technology fact sheet - trickling filters," 2000).

Opportunities for Resource Recovery from Waste Water

The mining industry and sanitation infrastructure have the potential to utilize important wastewater components. Technologies such as SAVMIN, SPARRO, Biogenic Sulphide, and DESALX have

demonstrated efficacy in salt and water recovery, with some achieving greater than 95% recovery, indicating considerable resource reclamation. These technologies include several separation techniques for efficiency and commercial application (Matebese et al., 2024). Municipal wastewater in Zambia is a rich source of freshwater, energy, and nutrients. Water utility companies should look into it as an emerging water source to address future urban water demands. The wastewater has a high chemical energy and nutritional content, with an average potential of 16.2 kJ/g COD. Biogas production from municipal waste water management systems has great potential in Zambian cities. However, a feasibility study is required to address obstacles and opportunities for biogas power generation. Technical capacities in urban contexts must be aligned with feasible business strategies (Shane et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2022; Zhang & Liu, 2021, 2022). Treated wastewater has a wide range of applications, including industrial use, agricultural irrigation, groundwater recharge, and effluent quality enhancement. It can also be used for domestic activities including as firefighting, car washing, and toilet flushing (Becerra-Castro et al., 2015; Zarei, 2020).

Risks and Consequences of Water Pollution Associated with Waste Water from Mining and Sanitation Facilities

Despite its importance to socioeconomic growth, mining is regarded as one of the most harmful human endeavors, particularly in terms of water supplies in semi-arid regions. Unfavorable meteorological conditions can exacerbate the effects of mining operations, making it difficult to manage water supplies in these regions (Paraguassú et al., 2019; Santana et al., 2020). Water supplies are critical to economic growth, but resource depletion and human habitat degradation are compounded by population increase, urbanisation, industrialization, and agricultural activities, necessitating immediate conservation initiatives (Mhlongo et al., 2018). Mining has an impact on the environment of land, water, and air, with acid mine drainage (AMD) being a prominent concern. The environment is protected from

start-up to site decommissioning through guidelines and legislation. AMD is distinguished by excessive acidity, dissolved metals, and sulphates, necessitating treatment to eliminate acidity and reduce suspended particles (Kefeni et al., 2017).

Water Quality of the Kafue River

The Kafue River in Zambia, an important river system that traverses cities and villages, is suffering substantial degradation and potential loss of biodiversity. The river, which travels north-south throughout the country before emptying into the Zambezi, accounts for 12% of the Zambezi River's average annual runoff at its junction. It covers 152,000 km² and has an average annual runoff rate of 350 m³/s (Kambole, 2003). More than 80% of human waste water goes untreated, contaminating the ecosystem and triggering over 50 diseases. Inadequate water quality is linked to half of all child deaths and 80% of all worldwide illnesses (Lin et al., 2022). Zambia's mining, industrial, agricultural, and municipal sectors have discharged pollutants and effluents into the Kafue River, causing water quality to deteriorate. Increased eutrophic conditions, heavy metal concentrations, and suspended particles have resulted in the spread of *Salvinia molesta*, lower fish capture and size, and an unpleasant taste in the water. Fishermen have voiced discontent with the apparent loss of flavour, as well as a drop in fish capture and size in specific river sections (Kambole, 2003).

Importance of Mining and Sewage Waste Water Treatment before Discharge

Mining, despite being a major source of water pollution, contributes to economic growth through technical innovation, educational benefits, resource allocation, and community improvement initiatives, which generate jobs and revenue for local and national economies (Zahoor et al., 2022). Mining precious metals such as gold, copper, arsenic, mercury, cyanide, and uranium frequently generates hazardous metalloid ions, such as arsenic, which is typically derived from mining activities associated with minerals such as sphalerite, pyrrhotite, and chalcopyrite (Eberle et al., 2021; Zahoor et al.,

2021). Heavy metal pollution in terrestrial and marine environments is a major environmental concern, resulting in health problems from mining operations. The majority of heavy metals occur naturally, with only a few originating from human activities. Large metals have a high atomic mass and are harmful to life forms, polluting the environment and atmosphere and potentially endangering humanity (Mitra et al., 2022). Heavy metals can become very hazardous when mixed with other environmental factors including water, soil, and air, and humans and other living organisms may be exposed to them through the food chain (Mitra et al., 2022). High levels of antimony and chromium can promote cancer, whilst lead poisoning can cause intellectual impairments in youngsters. Mercury toxicity can produce Minamata illness, whereas cadmium poisoning can cause Itai-itai disease. Metals can be hazardous to the kidneys, brain, liver, skin, and heart. People should relocate away from industrial zones (Hou et al., 2013; Mitra et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2013). To prevent environmental and public health hazards, mining wastewater must be adequately treated before it is released into the environment (Matebese et al., 2024).

Poor sanitation causes millions of fatalities each year from sewage-related diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and diarrhoea (Sims & Kasprzyk-Hordern, 2020). The improper dumping of untreated sanitary wastewater endangers both human health and the ecology of water resources (Alwadani & Fatehi, 2018). Wastewater treatment is critical for decreasing water pollution since the primary source is the discharge of contaminated wastewater into surface or groundwater resources (Jerry A. Nathanson, 2024).

Solutions to Improve Mining Wastewater and Sewage Management

The treatment of mining wastewater is critical for decreasing pollution and protecting human health. Advanced treatment technologies, such as membrane filtration, reverse osmosis, and oxidation, can remove heavy metals and organic contaminants effectively. Natural techniques like bioremediation and phytoremediation are also

cost-effective. Closed-loop water recycling systems can reduce wastewater discharge quantities. Environmental standards must be effectively enforced and regulatory structures strengthened. Involving local communities and stakeholders in decision-making increases transparency and accountability. Capacity-building programmes for mining staff on wastewater treatment procedures are critical for proactive problem resolution. These approaches promote responsible wastewater management and contribute to sustainable mining operations (Babel & Kurniawan, 2003; Kafle et al., 2022; Kinnunen et al., 2021; Matebese et al., 2024; Mbewe, 2017).

Legal Provisions for Waste Water in Zambia

The Natural Resources Act of 1970 established Zambia's environmental regulatory framework, which was further expanded by the Game Parks and Birds Act of 1971, the Zambezi River Authority Act of 1987, and the Environmental Protection and Pollution Control Act of 1990. These legislations attempted to safeguard nature and wildlife while also establishing the Environmental Council ("The Environmental Protection and Pollution Control ACT," 1990).

Legal Framework for Water Pollution Control in Zambia

The **Zambian Constitution (Amendment) Act (No. 2 of 2016)** addresses a wide range of issues, including traditional rights, economic, social, and cultural rights, gender equality, natural resource management, indigenous peoples protection, environmental conservation, sustainable development, renewable energy promotion, the polluter pays principle, pollution management, public participation, agricultural land management, and water access rights ("Constitution of Zambia Act, 2016," 2016).

Environmental Management Act, 2011

This Act provides for integrated environmental management, conservation, and sustainable use of natural resources. It is divided into 12 Parts covering various aspects including the Zambia

Environmental Management Agency, pollution control, public participation, and environmental impact assessments. The Act mandates the publication of a State of the Environment Report every five years and a National Environmental Action Plan every ten years. It also allows the Minister to designate environmentally protected areas and implement biodiversity conservation measures (www.parliament.gov.zm).

Environmental Management (Amendment) Act, 2023

This Act amends the 2011 principal Act by: revising the functions of the Zambia Environmental Management Agency, aligning solid waste management provisions with the 2018 Solid Waste Regulation and Management Act, domesticating the Kigali Amendment to the Montreal Protocol, providing for the registration of pesticides and toxic substances, revising summary penalty provisions and addressing related matters (www.parliament.gov.zm).

The Water Resources Management Act of 2011 addresses a wide range of water management issues, such as freshwater and groundwater resources, surface water, water quality, pollution control, institutional frameworks, aquaculture, basin management, climate change adaptation, wastewater discharge, enforcement, environmental planning, flood control, monitoring, protected areas, river basin institutions, water abstraction regulation, conservation zones, water rights allocation ("The Water Resources Management Act, 2011," 2011).

The Mines and Minerals Development Act of 2015, as amended by the Mines and Minerals Development (Amendment) Act No. 14 of 2016, governs environmental impact assessments, soil quality, pollution, conservation, mining operations, exploration initiatives, soil restoration, and freshwater quality management, including pollution prevention measures ("The Mines and Minerals Development Act, 2015," 2015).

Zambia's environmental legislations have greatly improved governance, resource management,

and sustainable development. They protect biodiversity, boost economic growth, improve public health, and encourage renewable energy and eco-tourism initiatives. These legislations bring Zambia into line with international environmental agreements, boosting its global reputation and encouraging collaboration on environmental challenges. (Bennett & Satterfield, 2018; Fernandez & Shaw, 2016).

Shortcomings of Legal Provisions in Ensuring Waste Water Management

The legal provisions for mining and sewage wastewater management in Zambia are criticized for many shortcomings, compromising environmental preservation and public health. These include ineffective enforcement mechanisms, restricted public participation, a fragmented legislative framework, conflicting mandates, and inadequate monitoring. These concerns contribute to unchecked pollution and associated risks, necessitating immediate regulatory reforms and capacity-building measures to successfully manage them (Lemos & Agrawal, 2008).

Discussion

The review identified significant findings necessitating reflection and solution-finding regarding water pollution, particularly from mining and sewage wastewater. Despite treatment efforts, waste water still contains notable pollutants, notably heavy metals, sulphates, and various chemicals associated with mining and sanitation activities. Surface water pollution, evidenced by elevated pollutant concentrations in stream sediments and the Kafue River downstream of mining and sanitation operations, poses a threat to aquatic ecosystems and public health, although the river's self-purification capacity limits contamination. However, tributaries near mining centers often exceed Zambian effluent standards. Alkaline pH values in contaminated zones exacerbate risks to aquatic life, although complete destruction is not observed.

Mining operations contribute to environmental pollution through inadequate treatment, tailings dam leaks, and pipeline breakdowns, harming

water bodies, river sediments, and aquatic life. Effluents with high pollutant concentrations have led to animal eradication and reductions in algae and fungal populations. Tailing storage facilities lack comprehensive toxin treatment methods, restricting their ability to handle heavy metals, chemicals, and microorganisms effectively. Similarly, sanitation facilities contribute to watercourse pollution through sewage overflow, leaks, and insufficient treatment, with pollutants including fecal and total coliforms, nutrients, oils, and heavy metals.

Inefficiencies in municipal wastewater treatment plants, including high energy consumption, odor emissions, and low treatment efficiency, limit their effectiveness. Stabilization ponds suffer from high levels of biological oxygen demand and total suspended solids, along with long retention times. Eutrophic conditions, heavy metals, and suspended particles have facilitated the spread of *Salvinia molesta*, leading to decreased fish capture and size, and an unpleasant taste in water.

Effective wastewater treatment is crucial for reducing water pollution and safeguarding human health and the environment. Initiatives promoting recycling and resource recovery can minimize waste generation. Utilizing modern technologies like SAVMIN, SPARRO, Biogenic Sulphide, and DESALX, which have demonstrated high efficacy in salt and water recovery, can significantly contribute to pollution reduction. Municipal wastewater, rich in freshwater, energy, and nutrients, could serve as an emerging water source to address urban water demands, with biogas production holding potential for Zambian cities.

Addressing legal disparities between departments is recommended for effective water pollution enforcement. Feasibility studies are essential to assess the viability of innovative initiatives and overcome potential obstacles. Ultimately, concerted efforts across sectors are imperative to mitigate water pollution and ensure sustainable water management practices on the Copperbelt Province of Zambia.

Conclusion

Lastly, examining water contamination in Zambia's Copperbelt Province reveals a complicated network of issues and prospects for long-term management. The presence of pollutants derived from mining and sewage wastewater needs immediate reflection and problem-solving measures. Despite existing treatment efforts, the persistence of heavy metals, sulphates, and other pollutants highlights the need for more advanced techniques. Surface water contamination, as seen from the Kafue River and its tributaries, poses serious hazards to ecosystems and public health, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive response.

Mining operations, together with inadequate sanitary facilities, contribute significantly to environmental deterioration, affecting water bodies and aquatic life. The inefficiencies of conventional wastewater treatment plants worsen the problem, forcing a paradigm change towards more efficient and sustainable technology. Initiatives promoting recycling, resource recovery, and the use of advanced treatment methods present attractive opportunities for pollution reduction.

However, addressing legal discrepancies and completing feasibility assessments are critical stages towards successful implementation. Sustainable water management practices can only be realized via joint efforts across sectors, protecting both human health and the environment in the Copperbelt Province of Zambia and beyond.

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